

Strategic Management Project

Founder: Annie Khalid (Clothes Designer)

Mission Statement:

AK Design aims to harness creativity, provide exceptional quality, and offer a wide variety of clothing by applying the latest software design. We aspire to make a difference through our branding and stay ahead of fashion trends and market changes. Our brand will delight customers through an exhilarating online shopping experience and will everlastingly provide great value to our customers. We will enhance long-term positive change and improve living conditions by investing in ideas, people, employees, and communities.

Evaluation of Mission Statement:

Components	Yes	No
Concern for employees	✓	
Technology	✓	
Product/Service	✓	
Concern for public image	✓	
Profitability/Sustainability	✓	
Customers	✓	
Markets	✓	
Philosophy	✓	
Self Concept	✓	

Vision Statement:

We strive to become a global leader in fashion-knit and outerwear by empowering innovation and trendy designs and providing ultimate customer satisfaction.

Competitors:

Shereens

Khay

Hanias

Waw-reenas

Budget:

Startup costs can vary significantly across different clothing lines. Still, in general, a small-sized clothing line will need a minimum of 50,000 to get started, a medium-sized line will require 50,000-100,000 for startup costs, and an extensive line will need approximately 1.5 million upfront.

The start-up capital of AK Design was 100,000-150,000.

History:

AK Design's founder, Annie Khalid, started her clothing line a year ago, and it has a small setup at home. Later on, AK Designs expanded its clothing line by manufacturing unstitched fabrics. Huge capital was required to start a clothing line. This boutique manufactures a vast variety of garment types, ranging from casual wear to luxury wear. The manufacturer and subcontractor are two industries used to carry out production. Starting a new company from scratch was not easy; challenges arose, but the founder was prepared for peaks and valleys as she embarked on her clothing business journey. She envisioned that all of today's iconic brands started from somewhere.

Organizational Structure:

Managing Director

Finance manager

Designing manager

Marketing manager

Social Media Marketing Manager

Supplier and Logistics Manager

Procurement manager

Tailors (3)

SWOT Analysis:**Strengths**

- Strong online presence with 80% community engagement
- Unique designs and fabrics of clothes
- Exquisite quality of clothes
- Designers possess knowledge of fashion trends
- Adaptability to changing conditions
- Deliver clothes worldwide

Weaknesses

- No physical store

- Lacks diversification
- Low efficiency and high waste
- Slower to market than competitors
- An expensive range of clothes

Opportunities

- The trends are changing rapidly, thus creating rising opportunities for creativity and innovation.
- Adding men's and kids' clothing lines to its portfolio, which will lead to approximately a 50% increase in sales
- Improved lifestyle, hence more spending on luxury products
- Environment-friendly packaging
- Promotion through social media influencers

Threats

- Growing competitors in the clothing business
- Unstable environmental conditions
- Fast-paced changing fashion trends and third-party suppliers decrease profit margin.
- Huge threat of replicas

PESTEL Analysis:

Political:

Political factors are unanticipated and uncontrollable factors that significantly impact business. Political instability could add a risk factor and lead to a significant loss. The Pakistan government has faced uncertainty due to disagreements between political parties, frequent strikes, and changing governments. The political factors have the power to change results. It can also affect government policies at the local and federal levels. Similarly, AK Design is also affected by different policies, rules, and regulations. Hence, it should be ready to deal with local and international political outcomes. High import tariffs can compel consumers to buy from local manufacturers.

Economic:

The propensity to spend has been showing a positive trend in Pakistan from 2020 to 2022. This factor will positively affect the sales and profitability of our clothes because people in Pakistan have high spending in this industry. However, fashion is a luxury for the low-income group (which constitutes around 47 percent of the total population) in our country due to inflation. In comparison, the middle class is the majority who prefer to buy affordable clothes. A rising trend of renting clothes has also been observed to cope with inflation. Pakistan currently has a fluctuating interest rate of 15%, owing to a negative impact on the income of the apparel business. The inflation rate is escalating due to the recent flood disruption, adversely affecting

consumer spending. AK designs can cope with the current conditions by adopting the trend of renting formal and luxury clothes. It can offer clothes at competitors' rates since the prices of its clothes are higher than those of its competitors.

Social:

Social factors include age distribution, population growth, health consciousness, etc. Socio-cultural factors have a direct influence on the fashion industry. In Pakistan, forecasts have shown that there are more consumers in the 25-34 years segment than in other segments. Most of our industry customers include teenagers and young adults, and our business mainly targets those customers. Additionally, our customers' changing trends and tastes bring an opportunity for our company. Celebrities and social media influencers drive changes in the fashion industry and inspire others to follow their style. Another factor is corporate social responsibility, which significantly impacts the sales of all businesses, especially apparel. Increased awareness has led customers to purchase products or services whose brands actively give something back to society.

Technological:

Emerging technological changes have increased customers' inclination towards online shopping due to its convenience and cost-effectiveness. Platforms are available for reviews of customers, where customers are given the authority to provide feedback about the product. Nowadays, customers' buying behavior is highly affected by experiences shared by other customers who have made the purchase. These technological developments have also made the fashion industry more volatile, thus increasing the demands of its customers. Moreover, innovation has also improved interactions among retailers, wholesalers, and manufacturers due to more efficient communication channels. Online advertising and marketing are cheaper than conventional marketing methods. Even though the technology has resulted in automation in many businesses, the fashion industry is still labor-intensive due to changing trends and customer demands.

Environmental:

Environmental factors significantly impact all production and distribution units of all industries. For instance, global warming and climate change have made our environment vulnerable to disasters like floods, droughts, and tsunamis. The floods witnessed in Pakistan had severe consequences for people living there. It devastated people, as many of them lost their livelihoods, and more worrisome is the scarcity of food. This adversely affected the spending power of the victims of the floods. The floods did not affect AK Design, which has its operations in the Twin Cities.

A rising trend towards sustainable fabrics has been observed worldwide due to increased customer awareness to protect the environment. However, many reputable brands are shifting towards sustainable products, thus attracting customers. AK Design incorporates ethical practices in its business operations for a sustainable societal impact. AK Design can also become a

sustainable brand by following the UN Sustainable Development Goals. It can take into account environmental, societal, and waste considerations.

Legal:

Legal factors affecting a company include labor laws, environmental laws, tax policy, trade restrictions, and so on. A firm needs to be adaptable to follow future legislation and adjust its strategy accordingly. The firm needs to provide the fundamental rights of consumers and labor. AK Designs follows consumer, labor, and trade legislation to ensure equitable and safe treatment for all concerned parties.

Internal Factor Evaluation:

Strengths	Weight	Rating	Weighted Score
Strong online presence with 80% community engagement	0.08	2	0.16
Unique designs and fabrics of clothes	0.1	3	0.3
Exquisite quality of clothes	0.1	4	0.4
Designers possess knowledge of fashion trends	0.08	3	0.24
Adaptability to changing conditions	0.09	2	0.18
Deliver clothes worldwide	0.09	3	0.27
Weaknesses			
No physical store	0.1	4	0.4
Lacks diversification	0.1	3	0.3
Low efficiency and high waste	0.08	2	0.16
Slower to market than competitors	0.08	2	0.16
An expensive range of clothes	0.1	3	0.3
	1		2.87

External Factor Evaluation:

Opportunities	Weight	Rating	Weighted Score
The trends are changing rapidly, thus creating rising opportunities for creativity and innovation	0.06	3	0.18
Adding men's and kids' clothing lines to its portfolio, which will lead to approximately a 50% increase in sales	0.2	4	0.8
Improved lifestyle, hence more spending on luxury products	0.1	3	0.3
Environment-friendly packaging	0.05	2	0.1
Promotion through social media influencers	0.08	3	0.24
Threats			
Growing competitors in the clothing business	0.1	4	0.4
Unstable environmental conditions	0.1	2	0.2
Fast-paced changing fashion trends	0.15	3	0.45
Third-party suppliers decrease profit margin	0.09	2	0.18
Threat of replicas	0.07	3	0.21
	1		3.06

Critical Success Factor:

	Annie Khalid			Haniyas		Waw-reenas	
Critical success factor	Weight	Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted Score
Product Quality	0.1	3	0.3	3	0.3	3	0.3
Product Variety	0.09	2	0.18	3	0.27	3	0.27
Price competitiveness	0.1	2	0.2	2	0.2	2	0.2
Customer service/ loyalty	0.1	3	0.3	3	0.3	3	0.3
Brand reputation	0.09	3	0.27	3	0.27	3	0.27
Online Availability	0.04	4	0.16	3	0.12	4	0.16
Geographical coverage	0.06	2	0.12	1	0.06	1	0.06
Advertising/ marketing campaigns	0.08	2	0.16	3	0.24	3	0.24
Environmental sustainability	0.07	1	0.07	1	0.07	1	0.07
Profitability	0.05	3	0.15	3	0.15	3	0.15
Financial Position	0.05	2	0.1	2	0.1	3	0.15
Market share	0.04	1	0.04	2	0.08	3	0.12
Growth	0.05	2	0.1	3	0.15	2	0.1
Social Responsibility	0.08	2	0.16	2	0.16	2	0.16
	1		2.51		2.47		2.55

Strategies:

Present Strategies:

Future Strategies:

Integration Strategies:

AK Design uses forward integration because it has no distributors and supplies its customers directly. It has close relationships with only a few suppliers and demands a higher quality from those suppliers (Backward Integration).

Intensive Strategies:

AK Design will use a market penetration strategy by increasing marketing to capture a greater market share. The marketing efforts will be improved by increasing the marketing budget and offering sales promotion discounts and items (sponsored online marketing).

